

FRATERNAL COHESION LEVEL AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP TO PARENTAL ABSENCE AMONG A SAMPLE OF PREPARATORY STAGE STUDENTS IN JORDAN

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Abstract

This study aimed to identify the fraternal cohesion level among a sample of preparatory stage students in Jordan, and explore the relationship between parental absence in fraternal cohesion and the effect of absence on the fraternal relationship; The sample consisted of (446) students. The results also showed differences due to gender in the fraternal relationship scale in favor of males, except dimension: Relationship between brothers and sisters in favor of females. In addition to the existence of differences due to parental absence in the fraternal relationship scale in favor of the absence of the mother dimension: Responsibility feeling in favor of the absence of both parents, and found the effect of the interaction between the gender and parental absence on the brotherly relationship scale except for the dimension: Relationship between brothers and sisters, there was no interaction.

Keywords: Fraternal Cohesion, Parental Absence, Preparatory Stage Students, Jordan.

INTRODUCTION

Sibling relationships play an important role in the life of a sibling more than the company of parents does. They are mutual relations that tend to be equal and symmetrical with family members than other generations and evidence of the general state of family cohesion. Sibling relationships are also considered one of the best achievements that parents achieve in their lives, it is the first friendship for children, and the relationship between siblings is seen as somewhat complicated, especially in childhood, as they cannot live without the other despite the conflicts and arguments that occur from time to time and the other among them. They may show a desire to compete in some moments of life, while others show great love and affection for them. In adulthood, things begin to become clearer and to learn to appreciate and respect (Whiteman, McHale & Soli, 2012).

The older siblings may be a comfort and support deed for the younger siblings, as they help them in coping and give advice and guide on new conflicts that may arise in them, and they may play the role of answering questions and discussing topics that do not make them comfortable with the upbringing of a parent (Bryant, 1992). Fraternal relations are defined as the relationship that exists between fraternal children in light of family relationships and atmosphere to fulfill their desires and psychological, emotional, and social needs ... etc. whatever the goal (Aljawarneh, 2014).

The competition between siblings begins at an early stage in their life and may continue for life, and it is caused by obtaining attention and play. Competition and moderate conflict between siblings help to develop interaction between them, children who have competition and conflict with a level of warmth and support are more socially competent and emotional maturity. The family that is characterized by firmness and democracy lives its members in an atmosphere of encouragement and building positive fraternal relationships, while families that differ in patterns of parental treatment and non-interference in children's conflicts as something of no importance and are characterized by many problems among them, and it is noteworthy that 44% of brothers are characterized by intimacy and familiarity. While 34% agree with each other, and 22% are indifferent or aggressive. The reason for the social interaction in adulthood among the siblings is due to the safe attachment between them, and the sound educational standards that parents instill in their children. Siblings who have resentment and hostility towards each other are the result of deep and unresolved issues that have not been addressed or mitigated, due to differences in appreciation between the siblings, the surrounding circumstances, or the lack of communication between them. Siblings who can balance their experiences and interactions positively tend to build good health and continue it into adulthood, as it depends on the guidance of parents, and the siblings live together in the experience, so cultivating positive experiences and memories in children has a great impact on the continuation of relations between siblings (Schatz, 2010).

Feelings of jealousy and aggression come from parental bias towards some children, as children who feel parental discrimination and prejudice in their treatment show responses that are characterized by aggression and conflict towards brotherhood, And troubled fraternal relations greatly affect family relations on the one hand, and children and their social relations outside the family, on the other hand, The weak and shattered relations between siblings in preschoolers predicts the emergence of abnormal and anti-social behaviors towards others outside the school (Al-Araby & Zadry, 2013).

Traditional families have more parental control, in contrast to urban development families with less control, and females are more susceptible to this control than males (Hatab & Makki, 1981). In addition, children of one-person families have good physical and psychological health, children who live with a mother are healthier than those who live with their father, and children of familiar families of two people may face less interest, difficulty in interacting with others, and a lack of behavioral performance, in addition to lack of the influence of male parents on them (Berk, 2000; Hammer & Turnover, 1990). Aljawarneh (2014) pointed out that the tense fraternal relations affect the feeling of responsibility and acceptance from others and increase the future concerns of male and female children, and that relations between brothers and sisters increase cohesion and strength in the event of a stable and balanced family in all its different aspects.

Children learn through it the social behavior and access to the higher self that is done through example, advice, guidance, and punishment of wrongdoers; in addition to that, it plays an important role in encouraging and achieving the highest levels of ambition appropriate to their mental, physical and material levels. The mother's relationship with children has a great impact

on them and their behavior, as it is not only an elegant human relationship. The interaction between parents based on support, warmth, and encouragement achieves the proper growth of personality traits among children, such as a sense of independence and psychological and social harmony (Habib, 2010).

Parents are two members complementary to each other who support each other emotionally and spiritually, the emotional support of the mother by the father allows her to give the children most of what she has and give her the energy necessary to carry out the tasks required of her inside the home, the absence of the father leaves many negative effects on children, especially those who are in adolescence (Mason and Taheri, 2013).

The father may be absent from the family due to several reasons, including marriage with another woman, living with her away from children, infection with a specific disease, emigration outside the country, or the nature of the work he does, These reasons can affect the children's upbringing improperly, given that one of the parents is absent from the home and thus absent from carrying out the tasks that should be presented to his children, so they resort to relying on the mother to raise them away from the presence of the father, which leads them to an imbalance in their development (Mohsen, 2013). Parental absence is defined as the temporary or extended deprivation of one or both parents due to divorce, separation, death ... etc. because it has a great impact on the psyche of children as a result of lack of care, guidance, and access to psychological and social support (Rockemore, 2014)

Arif (2012) indicated that the disadvantaged parents tend to be more socially isolated than the non-deprived and that parental deprivation has a noticeable impact on the lives of adolescents and on building their social relationships during adolescence. Children who are absent from their parents permanently, such as death, are among the causes that are out of control and management, unlike absence due to travel or being busy with work for a long time. The matter leads to separation from the family, which in turn negatively affects the relationships and interactions within the family in general and the relationships between children in particular (Mayssoon & Taheri, 2013).

In addition, children of both genders are more likely to postpone gratification, have poor control over emotions such as anger and sexual satisfaction, and have poor knowledge of right from wrong (Parke, 1996). Moreover, that child is more likely to have problems with emotional and psychological adjustment, and show some wrong behaviors, and those who do not live with their biological parents are four times more likely to have emotional turmoil than others. Parental absence affects the structure of the family and creates disturbances in behavior, and aggression appears in childhood, reduced family relations, and an orientation toward individualism (Pfiffner, McBurnett & Rathouz, 2001).

They describe children who live without their parents tend to choose perverse mates, are more prone to problems that occur between them, in addition to being more aggressive, and have difficulty adapting to normal children (Horn & Sylvester, 2002). They are more likely to experience abuse and physical neglect, as well as emotional neglect (Sedlak & Broadhurst, 1996). And that adolescents who live without a parent, whether the mother or the father, are

more vulnerable to delinquency and criminal behavior, the commission of crimes within the school, possession, use or distribution of alcohol or drugs, possession of weapons, and attacks on the teacher, the principal or even his fellow student (Griffin, Bptvin, Scheier, Diaz & Miller, 2000). Mackey & Immerman (2004) noted that the absence of a father was more affecting the home than poverty, as it was a strong indication of the violent behavior of young people and the tendency to frequent imprisonment for them.

In Crockett, Eggebeen & Hawkins (1993) parents who have a presence between their children and the middle of their families convey a sense of family cohesion to their children and have a positive effective impact on cognitive development and their academic and behavioral compatibility, and this is evidence of the strong cohesive family relationship. And that the effective positive relationship between children and their parents has an effective impact on the compatibility of children.

Relationships based on love and acceptance of children and trust in them develop a son who loves others relates to others and trusts them, while inappropriate negative trends such as excessive protection negatively affect the children and their personalities, so past relationships are family relationships that complement each other and one of them is affected by negative consequences for all family members. Children with parental absence may live in an unstable family and social atmosphere, which is characterized by disturbed sibling relationships and access to emotional disorders such as anxiety and tension within the family. Adolescent students, the most members of the family who respond to pressures from their colleagues, may be exposed to many abnormal behaviors, such as behavioral or intellectual deviation, while female students begin to search for love and safety in others and adopt their behaviors and values and many other unhealthy habits (Heath, 2005).

Jordanian society has witnessed many rapid changes in recent decades, on various social, economic, and cultural levels. The emergence of a set of values against the traditional background and modern trends that prevailed (which were based on enhancing the importance of forming a large family, as well as strengthening the patriarchal authority and the authority of the elderly in the family), contributed to raising the level of education of women and increasing their participation in the labor market. It increased its assumption of life roles different from the traditional roles it used to perform, thus reducing its subordination to men and its social and economic empowerment. This accelerated change movement also led to the emergence of tangible shifts in the attitudes, trends, and aspirations of the population, which was characterized by its clear sensitivity towards concepts related to the pattern of polygamy; This reduced the chances of reproducing this pattern of marriage in Jordanian society (Karadsheh & Almasarweh, 2007).

It decreased dramatically, as these extended families constituted 10.9% in 2003, while in 2018 it became 1.5%, and 14% of families in Jordan are headed by women. Families have witnessed dramatic changes in recent years in response to economic and social changes, gender values, norms, and attitudes. Jordan witnessed a decline in marriage rates from 81,209 in 2014 to 70,734 in 2018, and a rise in divorce rates from 20911 in 2014 to 21,210 in 2018, and 85% of divorce cases are between ages the of 20-40 years (DOS, 2018).

The disturbance of the family atmosphere as a result of the loss of one or both parents or their separation leads children to instability and loss of confidence in themselves and the surrounding individuals, in addition to the loss of safety and fear of the future, Where the relationships between children inside and outside the family are affected, which leads them to fall into psychological and behavioral disorders that affect their personalities and family life. Parental absence also affects the development of children in their culture and personalities, as children suffer from emotional deprivation and loss of emotional balance that generates psychological conflicts, which leads them to fall into behavioral disorders and delinquency, they are characterized by low self-confidence and lack of commitment to discipline, lack of attention and loss of focus and response, and thus affect their psychological and mental development. Children who are absent from their fathers feel fear and depression, and their level of school achievement is affected. Accordingly, the problem of the current study arose, which is the level of fraternal relations and their relationship to parental absence among a sample of middle school students in Jordan. Then answer the following questions:

1. Are there differences between the genders in the level of fraternal cohesion in its dimensions (acceptance, future concerns, relations between brothers and sisters, responsibility feeling, parental bias) among students with parental absence?
2. Are there a statistically significant effect of the variable parental absence on the dimensions of fraternal cohesion?
3. Are there a statistically significant effect of gender or parental absence and the interaction between them on the dimensions of fraternal cohesion?

Study Objectives

The main aim of this study is to explore the relationship of fraternal cohesion to parental absence among a sample of middle school students in Jordan. The main objective is divided into identifying the level of fraternal relations, the differences between the genders in the level of fraternal relations, the effect of parental absence on fraternal relationships, and the effect of the interaction between gender and parental absence on the dimensions of fraternal cohesion.

METHOD

Study Approach

The current study followed the descriptive approach in one of the analytical forms, as it examined the level of fraternal cohesion and their relationship to parental absence. Moreover, the identification of gender differences and the impact of the interaction between the genders and parental absence on fraternal cohesion.

Participants

A total of (n= 1907) adolescent students with parental absence were selected using stratified Purposive sampling from ninth and tenth grade in the schools of the Qasabat Irbid educational directorate in Jordan. The sample was composed of 446 students, 240 (53.8%) male and 206 (46.2%) female students. There were 109 (24.4%) The father's absence, 127 (28.5%) The

mother's absence, and 210 (47.1%) parents together. Students ranged from 14.5 to 16 years of age ($M = 15.25$, $SD = 0.81$).

MEASURES

Fraternal Cohesion Scale

The researcher uses the fraternal cohesion scale for Aljawarneh (2014), as the paragraphs of this scale measure the interconnectedness and relationships between brothers and sisters themselves within the same family, or when the individual is at the center of attention, as the scale consists of (5) dimensions distributed into (30) items distributed on the following dimensions: The dimension of acceptance and has (6) paragraphs are (1-6), It is a psychological need for the individual to develop positive qualities and reduce negative behaviors; the dimension of future concerns and it has (6) paragraphs, which are (7-12), It is constant negative thinking about potential threats in the future; the dimension of relations between brothers and sisters and it has (6) paragraphs, They are psychological, emotional, and social interactions ... etc that take place between brothers within the family; which are (13-18), the dimension of responsibility feeling and has (6) paragraphs It is (19-24), The real feeling that makes its owner realize the size of the family tasks required of him, their health, social and ethical dimensions, and the ways to deal with them; the dimension of parental prejudice, and it has (6) paragraphs, which are (25-30), It is the distinction of one of the children and his preference for others in all respects. The scale contains 30 items designed to measure problems: acceptance, future concerns, relations between brothers and sisters, and responsibility feeling. Responses were rated on a 5-point scale ranging from 1 (scarcely) to 3 (Always). The validity of the scale (High Standards and Discrepancy) was supported by confirmatory factor analysis. Factor loadings for the items of this scale ranged from 0.55 to 0.93. Internal consistency reliabilities (Cronbach's alphas) for the scale in this sample were 0.92 (High Standards) and 0.94 (Discrepancy).

Procedure

Participants in the study were chosen from the ninth and tenth grades, and oral informed consent was obtained from all of them. The participants were asked to complete a demographic sheet. The participants completed the questionnaires in one sitting during class time and did not receive any compensation for their participation. The researcher oversaw the completion of the questionnaires.

Statistical Analysis

In the present study, mean and SD were used to the scores of respondents on the family conflicts scale, and two-independent samples t-tests were used to examine differences in scores on each of the fraternal cohesion scales by gender, and (One Way ANOVA) was used to adolescents estimates on the fraternal cohesion scale and by parental absence. (MNOVA) were used to identify the score respondents on the domains of the fraternal cohesion, and comparisons dimensional (Tamhane Test) were used to score respondents on the domains of the fraternal cohesion.

RESULTS

To find out the direction of these differences; the means, SD, account for the parental absence and groups, and a table (1) shows that.

Table 1: The mean and SD the scores of respondents on the fraternal cohesion scale and by parental absence

Domains	Acceptance		Future concerns		Relations between brothers and sisters		Responsibility feeling		Parental bias		Scale	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Father	1.53	0.46	1.50	0.46	1.45	0.36	1.29	0.39	1.52	0.62	43.62	9.77
Mother	1.90	0.42	1.95	0.43	1.74	0.32	1.26	0.35	1.66	0.66	51.09	10.74
Together	1.67	0.43	1.64	0.50	1.52	0.41	1.44	0.46	1.38	0.45	45.89	10.24

The table shows (1) that differences in fraternal cohesion scale as a whole was in favor of the mother's absence ($M = 51.09$; $SD = 10.74$); and for domains: Acceptance domain in favor of the mother's absence ($M = 1.90$; $SD = 0.42$); As for the future concerns domain in favor of the mother's absence ($M = 1.95$; $SD = 0.43$); and relations between brothers and sisters domain in favor of the mother's absence ($M = 1.74$; $SD = 0.32$); As for the responsibility feeling domain in favor of the parents absent together ($M = 1.44$; $SD = 0.46$); and finally parental bias domain in favor of the mother's absence ($M = 1.66$; $SD = 0.66$).

To see if there were differences between gender on domains of the fraternal cohesion scale, use a testing – t (T-test). It shows a table (2) means and SD, the results of the test (T).

Table 2: Test results (T) of the differences between the gender mean degrees on the fraternal cohesion scale

Domains	Gender	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Acceptance	Males	1.77	0.56	3.88	0.000**
	Females	1.61	0.36		
Future concerns	Males	1.72	0.56	1.03	0.316
	Females	1.67	0.42		
Relations between brothers and sisters	Males	1.56	0.47	-0.08	0.935
	Females	1.57	0.28		
Responsibility feeling	Males	1.49	0.46	7.99	0.000**
	Females	1.20	0.30		
Parental bias	Males	1.60	0.57	4.36	0.001*
	Females	1.37	0.54		
Scale	Males	48.83	11.66	4.49	0.000**
	Females	44.47	8.78		

* $P < 0.01$; ** $P < 0.0001$

The table shows (2) that there are differences statistically significant between the gender in the completely fraternal cohesion scale, ($T = 4.49$, $P < 0.0001$), with males ($M = 48.83$, $SD = 11.66$) scoring higher than females ($M = 44.47$, $SD = 8.78$). Regarding the difference between the

gender in all domains of the scale, the results were as follows: Acceptance domain ($T = 3.88$, $P < 0.0001$), with males ($M = 1.77$, $SD = 0.56$) scoring higher than females ($M = 1.61$, $SD = 0.36$). As for the responsibility feeling domain ($T = 7.99$, $P < 0.0001$), with males ($M = 1.49$, $SD = 0.46$) scoring higher than females ($M = 1.20$, $SD = 0.30$). In addition, parental bias domain ($T = 4.36$, $P < 0.01$), with males ($M = 1.60$, $SD = 0.57$) scoring higher than females ($M = 1.37$, $SD = 0.54$). While there are no differences between the genders in the two dimensions of future concerns ($T = 1.03$), and relations between brothers and sisters ($T = -0.08$).

To verify this question has been used (One Way ANOVA) to see adolescents' estimates of the fraternal cohesion scale and parental absence, mean, SD, to see the direction of the differences, and a table (3) shows that.

Table 3: Test results (One Way ANOVA) to see adolescents' estimates on the fraternal cohesion scale and by parental absence

<i>Domains</i>	<i>S.V</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>Df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>Value (F)</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Acceptance	Between G	9.115	2	4.558	24.90	0.000*
	Within G	81.077	443	0.183		
	Total	90.192	445			
Future concerns	Between G	12.813	2	6.407	28.95	0.000*
	Within G	68.762	443	0.155		
	Total	98.031	445			
Relations between brothers and sisters	Between G	5.910	2	2.955	20.83	0.000*
	Within G	62.852	443	0.142		
	Total	68.762	445			
Responsibility feeling	Between G	2.946	2	1.473	8.55	0.000*
	Within G	76.330	443	0.173		
	Total	79.276	445			
Parental bias	Between G	6.293	2	3.146	10.08	0.000*
	Within G	138.273	443	0.312		
	Total	144.565	445			
Scale	Between G	3608.671	2	1804.336	17.09	0.000*
	Within G	46776.882	443	105.591		
	Total	50385.554	445			

* $P < 0.0001$

The table shows (3) that there are differences statistically significant between parental absence in the whole fraternal cohesion scale ($F = 17.09$; $P < 0.0001$), and for domains: Acceptance domain ($F = 24.90$; $P < 0.0001$), as for the future concerns' domain ($F = 28.95$; $P < 0.0001$), and Relations between brothers and sisters' domain ($F = 20.83$; $P < 0.0001$), as for the responsibility feeling domain ($F = 8.55$; $P < 0.0001$), and finally parental bias domain ($F = 10.08$; $P < 0.0001$).

To verify this question has been used (MNOVA), and a table (4) shows that.

Table 4: Test results (MNOVA) score respondents on the domains of fraternal cohesion

<i>Domains</i>	<i>S.V</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Gender	Acceptance	7.162	1	7.162	42.84	0.000**
	Future concerns	2.218	1	2.218	10.40	0.001*
	Relations between brothers & sisters	0.139	1	0.139	0.99	0.320
	Responsibility feeling	10.825	1	10.825	73.45	0.000**
	Parental bias	8.274	1	8.274	29.12	0.000**
Parental Absence	Acceptance	13.752	2	6.862	41.05	0.000**
	Future concerns	1.544	2	7.772	36.45	0.000**
	Relations between brothers & sisters	5.729	2	2.865	20.43	0.000**
	Responsibility feeling	2.780	2	1.390	9.43	0.000**
	Parental bias	7.337	2	3.668	12.91	0.000**
Gender × Parental Absence	Acceptance	1.022	2	0.511	3.06	0.048*
	Future concerns	1.955	2	0.978	4.58	0.011*
	Relations between brothers & sisters	0.757	2	0.378	2.70	0.068
	Responsibility feeling	2.953	2	1.476	10.02	0.000**
	Parental bias	3.831	2	1.916	6.74	0.000**
Error	Acceptance	73.555	440	0.167		
	Future concerns	93.83	440	0.213		
	Relations between brothers & sisters	61.688	440	0.140		
	Responsibility feeling	64.844	440	0.147		
	Parental bias	125.034	440	0.284		
Scale	Acceptance	1375.056	446			
	Future concerns	1391.750	446			
	Relations between brothers & sisters	1159.583	446			
	Responsibility feeling	895.444	446			
	Parental bias	1139.583	446			

* P < 0.01; ** P < 0.0001

The table shows (4) that it is statistically significant in all degrees of differences in the domains of fraternal cohesion scale and the variables of gender and parental absence interaction between them except relations between brothers and sisters dimension in gender and the interaction of gender with parental absence, and to find the source of these differences will use (Tamhane Test) comparisons dimensional differences in degrees domains of fraternal cohesion the scale, so as is evident in the table (5).

Table 5: The result comparisons dimensional (Tamhane Test) scores respondents on the domains of fraternal cohesion

<i>Domains</i>	<i>Variable</i>	<i>Variable</i>		
		Father	Mother	Together
Acceptance				
	Father		-0.3861*	-0.1498*
	Mother			-0.2362*
	Together			
Future concerns		Father	Mother	Both
	Father		-0.4475*	-0.1429*
	Mother			-0.3046*
	Together			
Relations between brothers & sisters		Father	Mother	Both
	Father		-0.2952*	-0.0741*
	Mother			-0.2211*
	Together			
Responsibility feeling		Father	Mother	Both
	Father		-0.0311	-0.1445*
	Mother			-0.1756*
	Together			
Parental bias		Father	Mother	Both
	Father		-0.1461	-0.1343
	Mother			-0.2805*
	Together			

* interaction

Table shows (5) shows that there is an interaction in the acceptance dimension between the father and the mother (-0.3861), between the father and the two parents together (-0.1498), and between the mother and the parents together (-0.2362). As for the future concerns dimension, there was an interaction between the father and the mother (-0.4475), between the father and the two parents together (-0.1429), and between the mother and the parents together (-0.3046). About the distance between brothers and sisters, there was an interaction between the father and the mother (-2.952), between the father and the two parents together (-0.0741), and between the mother and the two parents together (0.2211-). In the sense of responsibility, the interaction was between the father and the parents together (0.1445-), and between the mother and the parents together (0.1756-). As for the parental bias dimension, there was an interaction between the mother and the parents together (-2.805).

DISCUSSION

The results showed differences due to gender in the fraternal relationship scale in favor of males, except dimension: Relationship between brothers and sisters in favor of females. In addition to the existence of differences due to parental absence in the fraternal relationship scale in favor of the absence of the mother dimension: Responsibility feeling in favor of the absence of both parents, and found the effect of the interaction between the gender and parental absence on the brotherly relationship scale except the dimension: Relationship between

brothers and sisters, there was no interaction. The researchers attribute this to the family incompatibility resulting from the lack of a sense of the value of family members and the exchange of positive feelings among them, and the children of families in which one of the parents is absent live in a turbulent family climate dominated, by lack of cohesion and poor relations with each other, and they are less confident in themselves and less compatible in their relationships inside and outside the family which makes them unwanted individuals most of the time. And children feel poor acceptance of others in the event of divorce and separation because they are seen as individuals fleeing from troubled families dominated by conflict, conflict, and the promise of stability.

The researchers believe that the absence of dialogue has a major and influential role in the weakness of relations between brothers. Sons in troubled families do not show any interest in brothers and the dialogues they provide to support family communication, so each works to form his world away from his brothers and sisters. This is due to the unpleasant experiences learned from the parents in how to communicate between them based on quarrels and constant conflict, which is transmitted to the children in their communication with each other.

The nature of society, family, and social upbringing values male children and favors them over females, and they are seen as more likely to face the damages resulting from the absence of one or both parents, and they can face biological pressures.

Perhaps the need for acceptance by males is one of their basic needs, especially in the absence of parents or one of them for any reason, as they seek approval and satisfy their needs for emotional security, expression, and belonging, and therefore because males in our Arab society in general and Jordan, in particular, strengthen their position as the nerve of the family and the main pillar in it, because of their dependence on him, when males do not obtain acceptance in the family first and society second.

They will suffer from isolation and failure to establish normal relations with others, so he has fears and low self-esteem, which makes him vulnerable to ridicule and ridicule from others and this leads them to not establish a stable family that enjoys emotional balance. In contrast to females, who find these matters in other family members, and in adulthood, they find them in a life partner.

The researchers also see that the social legacies and norms that society are accustomed to, so the Arab family upbringing is affected by male control and control, in addition to that raising males is easier than raising females, and they are the basis for this family and they are the ones who carry the family name for future generations. The most important thing that creates this bias between sons and daughters. This is what indicated by Hatab & Makki (1981) that traditional families have more parental control, in contrast to urban development families with less control, and females are more susceptible to this control than males.

The absence of the mother causes cracks and a deep rift in the psyche of the children, so the children who lost their mother feel the indignation of life on them, especially when the mother married someone other than his father, and he becomes an unwanted person between his brothers and sisters, whether they are on the part of the mother or the father.

So they tend to isolate and feel inferior because of a lack of acceptance for him, and lack of acceptance, especially in the early stages of their life, is one of the important matters that may return in adolescence so that adolescents work to fill this strong lack of love and tenderness, so they look for people of the same age who can satisfy what they seek. This is what indicated Al-Araby & Zadry (2013) that weak and shattered relations between siblings in preschoolers predict the emergence of abnormal and anti-social behaviors toward others outside the school.

The absence of the mother leads to psychological and family pressures, and it begins with fear and involuntary aversion of the children and concern about their future, as her absence leads to the emergence of emotional disorders that make it difficult for them to achieve balance in their future requirements, whether on the level of work or husband ... etc. and between the needs of the family that must be provided, whether psychological or Social or economic, adolescents fall into confusion and anxiety to face these difficulties and challenges, and these problems are further exacerbated in the absence of a teacher and a leader (mother) who helps children in the march of their lives. This is indicated by Habib (2010) that the mother's relationship with children has a great impact on them and their behavior and that the interaction between parents based on support, warmth, and encouragement achieves the proper growth of personality traits among children.

The researchers believe that most socially unacceptable individuals come from destabilized families who do not like their parents, and they become uncomfortable with them and trust them. Methods of abnormal parental treatment of negligence or excessive bullying and fluctuation in this treatment from time to time, in addition to the lack of interest in their behavior, create individuals who feel dissatisfied with themselves and frustrated and that they are failures, all of these will create a lack of acceptance of them by others, and this will be worse in the event of divorce, especially if the divorced mother marries another man who will not accept to raise her children from the previous husband.

And that the absence of one of the parents is one of the important things in the emergence of disputes between siblings, which leads to them disturbing the relations between the brothers, whether they are male or female. The eldest son tends to gain power and control what is smaller than him and be cruel to them, or the male sons try to control females, which leads them to troubled relationships to become a disjointed family that is not coherent, in addition to the lack of dialogue between children is reflected in their social upbringing, which affects adaptation and the harmony of their relations with each other. This is what he indicated Aljawarneh (2014) to that pointed out that the tense fraternal relations affect the feeling of responsibility and acceptance from others and increase the future concerns of male and female children.

CONCLUSION

The results of the current study are consistent with previous studies that used fraternal cohesion, they are recommended to be used in future research and as a diagnostic means by school counselors. In addition to Draw the attention of educational counselors in schools to follow up on cases of students with weak fraternal cohesion and develop treatment programs for them. And to emphasize families by providing a family atmosphere of tolerance, harmony, and love

to create a generation of children with emotional balance and personal psychological stability.

CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS

Clinical implications include strengthening fraternal communication to build trust, contain parental absence safely and allow access to psychological stability, and preparing family therapy programs for those who provide counseling and guidance services in schools.

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